

**THE SEARCH FOR PEACE AND
DISARMAMENT IN WORLD POLITICS**
AN APPRAISAL

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CERTIFICATION

I certify that this project work on “The search for peace and disarmament in world politics. An appraisal,” was completed by Omobuwajo Deborah Adeyinka of the Department of History and International Relations, Lagos State University, Lagos State.

In partial fulfillment of the requirement of the award of Masters in International Relations and strategic studies.

This essay has been approved by the department project committee.

Supervisor

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this essay to God, my everything, my strength and my salvation. My true friend and all time companion.

Thank you Father for your love.

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My acknowledgement goes to all the lecturers and staff, both in this department and others who have contributed to my education in this university.

My supervisor, Dr Adeniji, thanks for your support. My parents and siblings for your love and encouragement. My wonderful classmates, thanks for being a family in LASU.

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ABSTRACT

War is a natural phenomenon that dates back to the very beginning of human existence. Several attempts have been made at studying and finding solutions to this scourge called war. Peace is also a natural phenomenon. This is because when war ceases, there is a time of relative peace.

It is however troubling that the end of physical warfare does not mean the end of hostilities. This makes war probable. Also, the aftermath of any kind of war in terms of loss of human lives, infrastructure and so on, is always quite devastating. Thus, the period of “peace” is usually a recovery from the after effects of war.

In the early days, war was fought for the slightest reasons. Kingdoms could go to war over honour, light insults etc. the losses were usually quite great. However, nothing then could be compared to the magnitude of devastation a conventional weapon could cause.

As a result of the introduction of nuclear technology into warfare, a new phase of diplomacy has arisen. World affairs are now centered on war prevention and not war winning. There is a heightened anxiety over the effects of nuclear accident or an actual nuclear war.

Then study will examine war and its kinds, causes of war, and the future of modern warfare. It will also examine peace and the different approaches to peace. In addition, it will examine the likelihood of maintaining peace in the years to come.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Peace has continued to elude the world, despite several attempts made at securing and sustaining relative peace. War on the other hand seems more commonplace and in actual fact, inevitable in most societies. Several wars have been fought over the years and periods of peace have been few and far between. War seems to be an intrinsic feature even in animals as they fight over food, territory and females among other things. It therefore seems that man has an animal instinct to compete for possession of certain things. One could safely conclude that one of the causes of war is the problem of distribution of scarce resources.

According to the Cambridge International Dictionary of English, peace is a period of freedom from war and violence especially when people live and work together happily without disagreement.¹ War is also the forcible contention between states with the purpose of overpowering each other by armed force in order to secure certain demands or claims. Also, war is aggression and counter-aggression that involves the mutual destruction of lives and property at a given time.²

Wars vary in degree and intensity. According to Karl Von Clausewitz, the bigger the objective of a war, the more serious it tends to be. War has been throughout history, a normal way of conducting disputes between political groups. One must consider that the objectives of war are usually good in the eyes of those who go to war. Ranging from a defense of honor or territory to the annihilation of an 'impure race', each objective is a worthy cause to the warring factions.

¹ Cambridge international dictionary of English, (Cambridge university press, 1996) pg 1636.

² Jamiu Oluwatoki, Strategic Thought (Department of History and International Relations, LASU 2005) p.g..

According to Mr Jamiu Oluwatoki, through war and not peace, many states have been enlarged, peace has been restored and there have been many inventions. War always involves the destruction of lives and property. It is therefore safe to assume that normal humans would prefer to avoid the destruction and devastation that accompanies war.

KINDS OF WAR

It has been estimated that in 5,560 years of recorded human history, there have been 14,531 wars. That is 2.6135 per year. In diplomatic circles, we hear of different forms of war such as cold war, limited war, total war, conventional and unconventional war, guerilla war, political warfare, propaganda war, psychological war etc. however, Quincy Wright (1964) argues that war has been extended to include many kinds of hostile acts besides the direct use of armed force. It has also been defined as the use of organized force between two human groups pursuing contradictory policies, each group seeking to impose its policy upon the other.

MODERN WARS

The century from 1866 to 1985 witnessed so many wars. The number of wars has remained relatively constant throughout that period at eight or so per decade. The number of casualties has increased (aside from the peaks of twelve million for world war 2). Overall, both the number of wars and their cost has increased significantly over recent years.

In the fifty years before 1914, there were seven inter-state wars in Europe.

- a. The Austro-Prussian – 1866
- b. Franco-Prussian – 1870-71
- c. The war of Bosnia, Serbia and Prussia against Turkey – 1876-1878.
- d-g. The four Balkan wars – 1885, 1897, 1912 and 1913.

Between 1918 and 1945, there was only one external war in Europe. Meanwhile, while external wars declined in Europe, they became more frequent in Asia and Africa; this was largely due (pre- 1945) to colonial enterprise in these two continents and (after-1945) to anti-colonial wars.

We must take into consideration the six Arab-Israeli wars, the three Indo-Pakistani wars, the Gulf wars (Iran-Iraq operation storm, the two wars in East Africa). Latin America remained relatively stable. There have also been wars in Rwanda (Africa), Kosovo in Yugoslavia, the Indo-Pakistani war (over Kashmir) and the USA involvement in Afghanistan against Iraq (early 21st century), and Russian war in Chechnya. ³

OBJECTIVE

The study is aimed at providing an exposé on the problem of war and the steps towards peace since 1945. It attempts to highlight the causes of war with an attempt at proffering solutions to the problem of war. It will elucidate on warfare and its types.

The aim is to find other assurances of security, which will permit the total relinquishment of war as an instrument of national policy. It also attempts to throw some light on diplomacy and other forms of peaceful settlement of disputes. It also attempts to elucidate on the history of nuclear warfare and its attendant consequences. Finally, it attempts a prediction of probable scenarios of the future of the world, judging from contemporary events.

³ Ibid, pg 7.

SIGNIFICANCE

The study will be of great help to contemporary society because it discusses the prevalent problem of war and peace. It will offer a critique of laid down institutions or methods, and it will provide answers to certain questions. It could induce self-examination of laid down institutions. Also, relevant authorities may adopt correct attitudes. It will also focus on the security dilemma and the issue of fear and mistrust among nation-states.

SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

The study will cover the period of (1945-till date). It will focus on the prominent events within that time: Particularly wars of great magnitude and prominence. Moves towards peace will also be discussed during this study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Scholars have attempted to make broad assumptions to explain the causes of war. K.N. Waltz in his "Man, the State and War", argues that war can be caused by three things; man's nature; internal nature; nature of the international system.

According to Karl Von Clausewitz, war is a kind of duel in which the aim is to disarm your enemy so that you may impose your will upon him. He disagrees with the eighteenth century theorists who consider war a game. He insists that war is an act of force, and to the application of that force, there is no limit." In further defining war, he says that wars of whole nations, especially civilized nations always arise from a political condition and it entails having a political motive and is therefore a political act.

He then says policy will continue to permeate and influence the action of war. War is "continuing policy by other means." He sees it as not just a political act but also a political instrument. While political design is the object, war is the

means. He points out diversity in the nature of wars by saying the greater the motives for war; the more they affect the whole existence of the nation involved. He concludes that all wars are political acts.⁴

According to Immanuel Kant, the state of peace among men living side by side is not the natural state (*status naturalis*); the natural state is one of war. This does not always mean open hostilities, but at least an unceasing threat of war. A state of peace, therefore, must be established, for in order to be secured against hostility it is not sufficient that hostilities simply be not committed; and, unless this security is pledged to each by his neighbor (a thing that can occur only in a civil state), each may treat his neighbor, from whom he demands this security, as an enemy.⁵

METHODOLOGY

The research will range from information obtained from journals and newspapers to Internet research and other forms of print reports. The abundance of material is not surprising for a study of causes and effects of war alone would uncover a large collection of published and unpublished works.

⁴ Von Clausewitz, ON WAR. www.googlesearch.com. April 2007.

⁵ Immanuel Kant, Perpetual Peace: A Philosophical Sketch 1795. pg 3

CHAPTER TWO

THEORIES OF WAR AND PEACE

In modern times, war has become so costly, so destructive, so imprecise in its impact and unpredictable in its results that its continued use for the settlement of disputes is insupportable. Diplomacy is one of the oldest methods of conducting international relations. It is aimed at coping with the problem of war. Norman Paddleford defines diplomacy as a body of general routine, official interaction among non-warring states by which they communicate their policies and attempt to gain concessions. Richard Sterling defines it as “the use of language rather than force and the exchange of ideas rather than blows in the conduct of relations among societies.”⁶

At page 472 of volume 7, The Encyclopedia Britannica defines diplomacy as “A conduct and management of relations between sovereign states, in accordance with established rules and usages, with a view to obtaining maximum advantage for the diplomat’s own state, and with a minimum friction and resentment.”

The Oxford dictionary defines diplomacy as the management of international relations by negotiation, or the methods by which relations among nation-states are adjusted and managed by ambassadors and envoys. In this sense, the diplomat acts as an intermediary between his government and other governments.

Diplomacy is the art by which peaceful intercourse between and among states is facilitated and conducted and even when war breaks out, diplomacy is employed to facilitate the end of hostilities or to negotiate for a ceasefire or truce, pending armistice and eventual peace protocol and signed peace.⁷

⁶ Ifeoma Ezeabasili; International Relations, concepts and theories (Emmanuel concepts2005)pg 31

⁷ Akinjide Osuntokun, The genesis, Development and Practice of The Art or Science of Diplomacy, (topics and issues in International Relations, Femi Adegbulu 2006) p 51

It is assumed that the phenomenon of war has been regarded in many different ways. It has been viewed as a salutary exercise, contributing usefully to the development of men and of nations. It has been considered an inescapable reality, deriving inevitably from the nature of individuals. International organizations represent a denial of this contention; it assumes that war should be and can be prevented. Thus it presented a number of approaches to peace, deriving from different conceptions of the nature and causes of war.

In ordinary English language, diplomacy and tact are interchangeable. The art of diplomacy also involves cleverly advancing one's interest without drawing negative vibes to oneself or one's country. This is why sometimes people joke that diplomats are paid to lie in order to make their countries look nice in the comity of nations. This is perhaps overstating the case. But there is no doubt that diplomacy entails saying sometimes-difficult things or making obviously difficult demands by coating them with apparent pleasant platitudes.

PACIFIC SETTLEMENT AS AN APPROACH TO PEACE

The pacific settlement approach has been characterized by emphasis upon the problem of discouraging resort to war as a means of solving disputes. In dealing with this problem, the pacific settlement approach reveals a series of basic assumptions about the nature of war.⁸

In the first place, it is assumed that war is chosen as a settlement device because of the passions that are aroused by disputes. War is a kind of national temper tantrum; in the heat of anger, people fail to seek and refuse to use the rational means of solution, which are available, and losing their heads, rush rashly into

⁸ Inis Claude, *Swords into ploughshares; the problems and progress of international organization* (Random House Inc, USA 1956) p 218

war. To this end, champions of peaceful settlement have typically sought to impose delay to institute a “cooling off period, so that tempers may subside and temperate judgment may prevail.”⁹

The second assumption underlying pacific settlement doctrine is that war is often caused by ignorance and misunderstanding of the facts involved in an international crisis. The advocates of peaceful settlement have set great store by the institution of impartial commission of inquiry. If the investigators can putter around at some length, so much the better; but they can serve the cause of peace not merely by killing time, but also by allaying the misapprehensions and correcting the misconceptions of the disputants.

Thirdly, it is assumed that war results from international quarrels because of the pride of governments and people because they are too heavily involved in these situations to permit them to seek a more reasonable and less drastic solution.

Pacific settlement offers to inject into the dispute a disinterested party with whom negotiations may be conducted by states which have become too estranged to negotiate with each other, and to whom concessions can be made which either state would refrain as a point of honour from making directly to the other.

A further hypothesis is that states frequently go to war for lack of imagination; blinded by their aroused passions and wounded sensitivities; they are unable to conceive honorable schemes of mutual accommodation and consequently blunder into belligerence in a state of intellectual bankruptcy.

⁹ Swords into ploughshares, p. 219

Again, the concept of the third party becomes relevant. The function of the outsider is to exercise the creative imagination, which is the special gift of the dispassionate observer, bringing to the attention of the emotionally distraught participants the reasonable alternatives to a violent resolution of the dispute.

Finally, the traditional doctrine of pacific settlement has rested heavily upon the proposition that war is a product of selfish and cynical national leaders. Kant expressed the belief that the autocratic leaders were prone to go to war all too readily, since they stood to reap the gains of war without paying the price. The most obvious solution to this was proscribed by Kant and espoused by Wilson. "Let the people decide questions of war and peace."¹⁰

BALANCE OF POWER

Balance of power is seen as one of the ways of managing and controlling power. The term "Balance of Power" is used to refer to a situation where there is no preponderant power in the international system. This means that no state or group of states should become so powerful to be able to threaten others. If the balance or equilibrium is maintained, it is believed, there will be peace in the international system. Therefore, Balance of Power can either be at equilibrium at which point peace will be achieved, or at disequilibrium where peace cannot be realized.

Balance of Power has been used as policy by European states in the 18th and 19th centuries. As a policy, states deliberately come up with policies aimed at maintaining the power state equilibrium, and governments are guided by the assumption that unbalanced power is a threat to peace. Most of Europe therefore, pursued this as a foreign policy principle in the 18th and 19th centuries.

¹⁰ Swords into Ploughshares, p. 220

Sufficiently large numbers of independent states make alliance formation and dissolution flexible and easy. Military power is more important than ideological considerations. The objectives of war should aim at restoring the balance and unless the balance is lost, there should be no war.

A major power plays the role of balancer; it checks others that want to destabilize the balance. Britain played this role in the 19th century. The balance does not belong to any side but shifts in line with the equilibrium or the disequilibrium of the system. The permanent thing in the balancer is the interest in maintaining the balance.¹¹

COLLECTIVE SECURITY AS AN APPROACH TO PEACE

Collective security was the name given by the planners of a new world order after World War I to the system for maintenance of international peace that they intended as a replacement for the system commonly known as the balance of power. It involved the establishment and operation of a complex scheme of national commitments and international mechanisms designed to prevent or suppress aggression by any state against any other state by presenting to potential aggressors the credible threat and to potential victims of aggression, the reliable promise of effective collective measures, ranging from diplomatic boycott through economic pressure to military sanctions to enforce the peace.

Its advocates emphasized its differentiation from other methods, giving special attention to the argument that it was different from and superior to the system of competing alliances that was associated with the Balance of Power concept.

The assumption of collective security is simply that wars are likely to occur and that they ought to be prevented. The theory of collective security is not invalidated by the discovery that the causes, functional purposes and initiatory mechanisms of war are varied. Collective security may be described as resting

¹¹ International Relations; Concepts Theories and Analysis, pp 78-79

upon the proposition that the deterrent effects of overwhelming power upon states, which are too rational to invite certain defeat, can prevent war. In this respect, it is fundamentally similar to a Balance of Power system involving defensive alliances.

In contrast to pacific settlement, which is mainly concerned to evoke peaceful attitudes of quarreling states, collective security depends upon a positive commitment to the value of world peace by the great mass of states.

Collective security recognizes no traditional friendships and no inveterate enmities and permits no alliances with or alliances against. The principle of alliance tends to inject into international relations, a concept of the advance identification of friends and enemies that is alien to the basic proposition of collective security. Whoever commits aggression is everybody's enemy; whoever resists aggression is everybody's friend. Membership of the collective security system involves alliance with nobody in particular, but with everybody in general.¹²

PREVENTIVE DIPLOMACY AS AN APPROACH TO PEACE

The concept of preventive diplomacy, which is not to be found in the theoretical substructure of the charter of the UN, has emerged from the operating experience of the UN to join the peaceful settlement of disputes, collective security and disarmament as a major approach to peace through international organizations. This concept is irrevocably associated with the name of the late Dag Hammarskjöld, as collective security is tied to that of Woodrow Wilson.

Preventive diplomacy so labelled by Hammarskjöld represents his answer to the question of how the UN can be made directly relevant to the crucial struggle

¹² Swords into Ploughshares, p 262

between East and West. To him, it is an international version of the policy of containment, designed not to restrict expansion of one bloc or the other, but to restrict the expansion of the zone permeated by bloc conflicts; it was put forward as a means for containment of the cold war.

Hammaraskjold explicitly related his analysis to a series of cases, including the Middle East crises of 1956 and 1958, the Laos case of 1959 and the Congo crisis of 1960, in which the UN had “moved so as to forestall development which might draw the specific conflict, openly or actively into the sphere of power bloc differences.” Essentially, his theoretical essay was a set of reflections upon experience and a projection into the future of the role, which the UN had begun to evolve under his imaginative leadership.

All this is not to say that preventive diplomacy is utterly different from pacific settlement. The two approaches are alike depending upon the consent of the states immediately involved in the troubled situations for the introduction of international mechanisms; UN peacekeeping instruments, no less than the agencies of conventional peaceful settlement, are based upon this principle. They share the objective of contributing to the improvement or stabilization of relationships among parties directly involved in antagonism. The distinctiveness of preventive diplomacy lies in its substitution of global for local emphasis, its preoccupation with avoidance of the spread of cold war into areas affected by disputes, rather than with settlement of dispute *per se*. What it promises is not the solution of cold war disputes, but the restriction of the cold war arena.

The line between Preventive diplomacy and Collective security may not be obvious to the casual observer, for operations representing the former approach, like those associated with the latter are likely to involve the formation and utilization of an international military force of more than negligible size,

composed in the absence of a standing force of units made available from national military establishments.

The central objective of preventive diplomacy is to abort the development of situations where the need for operation of collective security might arise- that is, to prevent the extension of great power confrontations that might produce violent conflicts. Then emphasis here is not on the frustration of a “would-be” aggressor, but on the avoidance of intensified rivalry. The aim is not to threaten an expansionist state with defeat but offer the promise of assistance to competing states or blocs in limiting the scope of their competition. Helping all states to avoid war, rather than helping some states to resist attack is the theme of preventive diplomacy.

A collective security force in action aims to separate an aggressor, forcibly from his victim. A preventive diplomacy force in action aims to keep competitive powers, by mutual agreement, separated from each other.

While it would be rash to assume that calculated aggression is no longer a factor to be worried about or contended with in international relations, preoccupation with this phenomenon tends to inhibit the focusing of attention upon the most typical and quite possibly the most dangerous threat to peace and order in the present era; situation of actual and incipient turbulence in which rival powers may become so entangled that they cannot ultimately escape violent confrontation, despite their rational intent to avoid such an outcome. By inviting concentration upon the question of what conditions within the international system may make war unavoidable rather than who may engage in aggression, shifting the focus of concern from the deliberately adopted policies of states to the predicaments in which states may become enmeshed, the theory of preventive diplomacy encourages a realistic appraisal of and a constructive

approach to the critical aspects of the problem of world order as it presents itself to our generation.¹³

¹³ Sword into Ploughshares, p. 321

CHAPTER THREE

ARMS RACE AND NUCLEAR WEAPONS PROLIFERATION.

After the Second World War and the defeat of Germany and Japan by the allied powers, the world witnessed what is known as the cold war. According to Ifeoma Ezeabasili, the term cold war is used to describe the tension and suspicion between the eastern bloc (USSR) and (USA). It suggests that although there was no physical confrontation between them, the level of hostility was nearly equal to a state of war.¹⁴¹

Attention can be drawn to the 1962 Cuban missile crisis, which perhaps marked the most trying experience during the entire crisis.

A distinguishing feature of the cold war was that the two major actors in the conflict, the USSR and the USA mostly engaged the services of their satellites in the prosecution of the war. From Korea to The Middle East, from the Horn of Africa to Asia, the story was the same. Each of the major combatants armed its satellites with sophisticated weapons and urged them on to war.

It should be stressed that the cold war was essentially an ideological battle. The capitalist powers of the west were suspicious of Soviet intentions, especially against the backdrop of Stalin's undisguised intention to export the Soviet ideology to all parts of the globe. Since communism was perceived as evil and a threat to western economic stability, the west could not be expected to fold her arms.¹⁵²

As a result of the unified goal during the Second World War, the west teamed up with the USSR in order to defeat Germany and Japan. Immediately after the

¹⁴¹ Concepts and theories of International Relations, p. 32

¹⁵² Abolade Adeniji, Transformations in International Realitions since 1945, (A-Triad associates Lagos 2006) p. 48

common enemy was destroyed, that temporary unity was threatened. The allied powers had a series of important meetings during which Russians insisted on security as their priority. This was as a result of the losses (men and material), which they suffered during the war. The US and Britain emphasized the need for self-determination and free elections for the people of Europe generally.

As a result of the agreement, which was concluded between Britain and Russia in October 1944 in Moscow, the British acceded in principle to a Russian domination of Eastern Europe. At another meeting in Yalta in February 1945, the leaders of Britain, Russia and the US met and it was agreed that while eastern Europe would remain the sphere of influence for the soviets, the meeting however pledged allied assistance in the formation of interim governments in eastern Europe which were to be “broadly representative of all the democratic elements in the population”. Ideological differences inevitably exacerbated the dispute. The USSR fostered communism in the soviet occupied zone, while the other powers discouraged it in their areas. This eventually led to the cold war.¹⁶³

At the initial phase of the cold war, both sides were motivated more by fear than by aggressive designs, but each also perceived the other as indeed intent on aggression. The cold war was punctuated by dangerous confrontations between the United States and Soviet Union, one in Berlin and the other in Cuba both precipitated by Soviet assertiveness.

ARMS RACE

In simple terms, it means the continuous competitive increase in the military power of two or more states based on the conviction that it is only by retaining an advantage in such power relations can they ensure their national security and

¹⁶³ Transformations in International Relations since 1945, p.56

maintain supremacy over their opponents. During the cold war, for every move made by the US, the USSR measured up or superseded it.

The US was spending a mere 6% of its GNP on arms expenditure, while the USSR spent about 30%. The soviet economy suffered hence development in the country was jeopardized. This was contributory to the eventual collapse of the soviet state.¹⁷⁴

The development of weapon technology has introduced yet another element into the international power calculus. It was only in the course of the 19th century that technology began to produce weapons systems- initially in the form of naval vessels- that could be seen as likely in them to prove decisive, through their qualitative and quantitative superiority in the event of conflict. But as war became increasingly a matter of competing technologies rather than competing armies, they developed that escalatory process known as “the arms race”.

“Arms races” can no more be isolated than wars themselves from the political circumstances that give rise to them and like wars they will take as many different forms as political circumstances dictate. They may be no more than a process of competitive modernization of maintaining a status quo that commands general support but in which no participant wishes, whether from reasons of pride or of prudence, to fall behind in keeping his armory up to date.¹⁸⁵

The reasons for the arms race include; struggle for supremacy between the super powers; benefits derived from arms export especially to third world countries;

¹⁷⁴ Strategic Thought, p.17

¹⁸⁵ Michael Howard, The causes of war and other essays, (Unwin paperbacks 1983 London).p. 28

arms exporters exercise political leverage over the recipient countries; mutual suspicion.

NUCLEAR WEAPONS

Nuclear weapons represent a historically new form of weaponry, which, by their multiple and far reaching effects, provide a means of warfare whose mass destructive potential is unparalleled in human experience.

The essential part of a nuclear weapon is the nuclear explosive device or warhead. Warheads may be built into various kinds of missiles, gravity bombs, artillery shells and so on. The term “nuclear weapon” usually denotes both the nuclear warhead and the delivery vehicle that takes the warhead to the target, particularly when this vehicle is a missile. Over the years, both warheads and delivery vehicles have undergone significant processes of development and improvement ¹⁹⁶

The initial nuclear weapon states included; The United States of America, The Soviet Union, The United Kingdom, France and China. These states were followed by the recent nuclear weapon states which are; India, Pakistan and Israel. The intended nuclear weapon states include Iraq, Iran, and North Korea. It is believed that the more armaments a state acquires, the more pride it possesses. Armaments are acquired in order to be used. Thus, the possession of arms could lead to war. Though this is not wholly true, it could be in some cases. This is one of the reasons for the attempt to discourage further proliferation of nuclear weapons.

“Here we must visualize our earth after a catastrophic nuclear war. As many as half a billion people could perish as a result of the explosions, heat and

¹⁹⁶ Javier Perez de Cuellar, UN Secretary General’s Report, Nuclear Weapons: A comprehensive study. (UN, New York 1991) p. 9.

radiation. But that would not be all. Transportation, communication and industrial production would grind to a halt. Entire regions of earth would be contaminated with nuclear fallout. Maimed and diseased people would be scrambling frantically for shelter, food and medication. The fear of contamination would drive healthy citizens to treat potentially diseased ones as vermin to be quarantined or exterminated. The sight of heaps of mangled and scalded human bodies, the debris of fallen buildings, the scorched earth, the stench of death and the howling of the dying could all have totally unpredictable psychological consequences upon the survivors following the immediate effects of deadly coldness of “nuclear winter” will set in. In such a nightmarish situation, only the most tyrannical regimes would be able to maintain enough order for the distribution of food, shelter and medical treatment. This is a system that we certainly do not wish upon our children. But beyond wishes, it is important that we quickly develop effective safeguards against the madness of a total nuclear war and a world in which the living will envy the dead” 7.

CASUALTIES AT HIROSHIMA AND NAGASAKI

1. Burns including “flash” burns caused by the instantaneous heat and light radiations.
2. Mechanical injuries resulting from flying debris, falling buildings and blast effects.
3. Radiation injuries, due entirely to gamma rays and neutrons emitted at the instant explosions similar to the results of severe x-ray over exposure.²⁰⁸

A nuclear reactor contains a core fissile material (the fuel) within which energy is produced by sustaining a regulated chain reaction. The fissile material used varies between reactor types but it may be natural uranium (which contains 0.7% fissile U-235) or uranium which has been enriched to increase the

²⁰⁷ Pearson Rochester, International Relations: the global condition in the late twentieth century.p 263

percentage of U-235 to around 3%. Nuclear reactors also incorporate three other features; a means for regulating the chain reaction such as control rods for absorbing neutrons; a moderator, surrounding the fissile core, which is used for maintaining the chain reaction by slowing down faster neutrons so they can more easily hit nuclear and initiate fission and finally, a means for removing the heat produced from the reactor core by the chain reaction, which can provide the steam to drive turbines and generate electricity.

Nuclear reactors have been developed for four main purposes (1) to provide electricity for civil purposes; (2) for use as propulsion units in naval vessels, especially submarines;(3) for materials testing and research or experimental uses; and (4) to produce plutonium for military explosive purposes.

Nuclear weapons derive their energy from either the splitting of atoms (so-called fission weapons), or their combination (so-called thermonuclear or fusion weapons). Only atoms with a large mass such as uranium or plutonium (the fissile materials), are capable of being split, which fusion can occur in atoms with a very small mass, such as hydrogen, deuterium and tritium). A fission weapon works through the creation of an uncontrolled nuclear reaction, which literally splits the atoms. A fusion weapon is basically a fission weapon with a second fusion stage added, the fusion process resulting from the compression and heating of the hydrogen atoms by the primary fission device.

Nuclear weapons produce their energy in three distinct forms; blast; heat or thermal radiation; and nuclear radiation. Each form may result in extensive damage to human populations. Awareness of these effects stem from the two weapons dropped on Hiroshima and Nagasaki in 1945, which remains the only time nuclear weapons have been used. However, what is also known is that the weapons, which destroyed these Japanese cities, were relatively small in

comparison to the destructive forces generated by later testing of thermonuclear weapons. The largest weapon known to have been tested was estimated to be 58 megaton (58 million tons of TNT device) and was produced by the Soviet Union during the height of the cold war.

The long term and widespread effects of nuclear radiation were also confirmed when at 1.23am on 26 April 1986, a large explosion ripped the roof of the number four-power unit at the Chernobyl nuclear complex in the former Soviet Union. The devastation caused by this explosion of an operating nuclear power plant shook the world. And while a much more serious nuclear accident was prevented by the bravery of those who dealt with the immediate aftermath, the long-term consequences were still profound. Nuclear radiation was carried on the prevailing winds across several national borders resulting in large numbers of animals having to be destroyed and humans well outside the initial blast area suffering varying degrees of radiation induced illnesses.²¹⁸

The advent of nuclear weapons and their unprecedented capacity for wreaking destruction across national borders has transformed the globe. Aside from the acknowledged nuclear weapon states, several others have the capacity to construct nuclear devices at short notice and deliver them if necessary, by increasingly sophisticated means.

Concern about the spread of nuclear weapons has undoubtedly increased in significance on the global agenda since the end of the cold war. Since 1945, nuclear technology for civil and military uses has disseminated on a global scale. In 1945 only the United States possessed the technological capability to manufacture a nuclear weapon. By 1964, four other states had crossed the

²¹⁸ Walteryust, 1947 Britannica Book of the year, (encyclopedia Britannica, inc, Chicago. London. Toronto 1947)p 199

nuclear weapons threshold, an event traditionally understood as the testing of a nuclear explosive device. These states were the former Soviet Union (1949), the United Kingdom (1952), France (1960) and The People's Republic of China (1964). All five states have been defined by the treaty on the non-proliferation of nuclear weapons (NPT) as nuclear weapon states, this being a state which has manufactured and exploded a nuclear weapon or other nuclear explosive device prior to 1 January 1967.

With many nuclear suppliers and with the downturn in the global nuclear energy market seeming set to continue for the foreseeable future, there is concern that the guidelines for international nuclear trade will not be upheld and that it will become easier for nuclear proliferation to occur. Although for the most part, these concerns are unwarranted, as explained later in certain cases, disagreements about the nuclear intentions of a state can create discord among suppliers.

NUCLEAR INTENTIONS OF STATES

Traditionally, nuclear weapons acquisition tended to focus on the strategic or political rationales, which led first the United States, and then The Soviet Union, United Kingdom, France and China to seek nuclear weapons. The strategic motivation focused on the role that nuclear weapons played in the context of the Second World War and its immediate aftermath when initially they were seen as war-fighting, war-winning weapons. Later, attention shifted to the role that nuclear weapons played in deterrence; leading to the assumption that one of the principal motivations for acquisition was the deterrence of other nuclear weapon states.

In addition to the strategic motivations, the political benefits that nuclear weapons conferred on those states with the wherewithal to manufacture them

were also deemed significant; nuclear weapons were seen as the most modern form of weaponry and their custodians, by dint of their technological prowess, were automatically to be afforded a seat at the “top table of international affairs”.

It is now more difficult to explain the phenomenon of nuclear proliferation by resorting to a single variable. Increasingly, it is necessary to consider a range of variables, which may have an influence on nuclear proliferation decisions. These include such variables as technological dynamics, the idea that the very availability of nuclear technology and a cadre of trained nuclear scientists encourages acquisition; domestic imperatives, the notion that domestic political events may compel a state towards nuclear weapons; diplomatic bargaining, then acquisition of a nuclear capability can be used to influence or bargain politically with both perceived allies and enemies; non-intervention, that a nuclear capability can deter or prevent intervention by other states and finally economic factors, the idea that the very possession of nuclear weapons enables a state to extract economic concessions as part of a political bargaining process.

Another feature of the nuclear proliferation puzzle, which needs to be explained, is the motivation, which leads a state to abandon the nuclear weapon option (Mitchell Reis 1998). This refutes the technological determinist argument that once a state acquires the capability to manufacture nuclear weapons, it will automatically do so. A number of factors have been identified to account for a state’s decision to move away from nuclear weapons acquisition, including; a change in strategic circumstances such as forging or renegotiation of an alliance with nuclear weapon state, the encountering of technical difficulties in constructing a nuclear weapon, or a perception that the acquisition of nuclear weapons may increase rather than reduce vulnerabilities.²²⁹

²²⁹ Darryl Howlett, The Nature of Nuclear Weapons and their Effects(Unwin paperbacks1983 London)p 2

Today, states are no longer the sole focus of attention when considering nuclear proliferation as increasingly, the part played by non-state actors become significant. Studies conducted during the 1970s and 1980s on nuclear terrorism indicated that there were risks associated with particular groups acquiring a nuclear device or threatening to attack civil or military nuclear installations. One study conducted by the International Task Force on prevention of Nuclear Terrorism concluded that it was possible for a dedicated terrorist group to build a crude nuclear device provided it had sufficient quantities of chemical high explosives and weapons of usable fissile materials. More significantly perhaps in terms of thinking of the risks involved, it was also felt that such a group would be more interested in causing panic and social disruption by making a credible nuclear threat; detonating a nuclear device and causing mass killing and destruction.

In addition to these factors, we are only now beginning to explore issues such as nuclear smuggling and the possibility that ethnic groups involved in civil conflict might seek a nuclear option to further their political or military objectives.

Nuclear smuggling has recently been given heightened international media attention since the disconcerting discovery that materials suitable for making nuclear weapons may be being trafficked by several different groups in increasing quantities. A major concern is that while it is likely that some of the smuggling is being conducted by opportunist individuals or groups, there is also the possibility that transnational criminal organizations have also created an international nuclear black market operating across traditional state boundaries in weapon related technologies. (Williams and Black 1994).

EFFORTS TO CONTROL NUCLEAR WEAPONS 1970

Since 1970, the global nuclear non-proliferation regime has continued to evolve, strengthened by the international legal framework the treaty provided. In March 1971, the IAEA negotiated its so-called INFCIRC/153 safeguards document, which provides a model for all safeguards negotiated with parties to the NPT. Additional arrangements have also been established for the conduct of international nuclear trade.

There is a nuclear abolition movement that calls for the abolition of nuclear weapons in order to create a safer world, free from the threat of nuclear weapons. Nonviolent resolution of conflict is best accomplished through the support of international and national institutions like the United Nations, Int'l Atomic Energy Agency, etc²³10

All of these trends put together-globalization, mass communications, nuclear abolition movements, cost-benefit analyses- make nuclear war less likely and makes a strong case for the end of the nuclear age.

STOPPING SHIPMENTS

The Proliferation Security Initiative, which aims to intercept shipments, mostly at sea, is among a series of practical steps the US is taking to stop weapons of mass destruction trade to and from North Korea. Washington boasts that seventy countries now support the Initiative, and that actions involving partners have halted eleven proliferation transactions. Most would have been intercepted anyway, and several involved cooperation from China, so were not strictly speaking related to the Initiative.

²³10 The Nature of Nuclear Weapons and their Effects.p 3

Critics claim that not a single North Korean ship has been intercepted by the Initiative. It is too early to judge success, however, particularly given the difficulty of measuring its deterrence effect. The US is now trying to expand cooperation to air and ground interception, seeking agreements from Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, and Kyrgyzstan, for example, to deny over-flight clearance for suspect flights from North Korea. Washington is also taking action to disrupt financial flows that support proliferation networks.²⁴¹¹

²⁴¹¹ www.google.com, Post Cold War Nuclear Policy study questions, 2007

CHAPTER FOUR

ARMS CONTROL, DISARMAMENT AND THE SECURITY DILEMMA

Arms control and disarmament have appeared in the dictionary of international relations and strategic studies as measures aimed at controlling arms build-up thereby protecting the peace and security of the world. For instance, when Alfred Bernhard Stet, a Swedish industrialist and chemist invented dynamite in the 19th century, his intention was to discourage war and encourage peace.²⁵¹

He believed that peace could quickly unite and bring gruesome ruin to any aggressor. Nobel was convinced that no sane nation would provoke a conflict if the consequences to it would be devastating. However, less than twenty years after Nobel's death in 1896, the world war I (1914-1918) broke out, where the use of deadly weapons, including machine guns, poison gas, tanks, submarines, flame throws, airplanes and so on, leading to the death of no fewer than ten million soldiers and twice that number injured. The events of World War II (1939-1945) were more deadly in terms of sophistication and strategy.

Arms control is a concept, which emerged in the 1960's. It entails efforts to regulate armament in order to make war less likely and to integrate its effects if it occurs.

John Spanier defined arms control in the nuclear context as the process aimed at stabilizing mutual deterrence and avoiding nuclear war by eliminating the incentive to strike first at the other side. Henry Kissinger believes that arms control is another form of diplomacy. He said that arms control was the reverse side of the "positions-of-strength" approach to the concept of armament.²⁶²

²⁵¹ Mark Fitzpatrick (Senior fellow for non-proliferation), World Today, www.google.com 2006.

²⁶² Awake, May 8, 2002 p. 3

Doufherly and Pfalzgraff define arms control as a situation whereby “nations will continue to possess arms and aim at managing them to enhance security and promote desirable political and strategic objectives, rather than allowing weapons technology to dictate policies in ways that reduce the safety and controllability of the international environment. Arising from the above definition is the fact that arms control policies typically seek to impose some kind of restraint or regulation on the qualitative design, quantitative production, method of deployment, protection, control, transfer and planned, threatened or actual use of military forces and weapons.

It is important to stress that the philosophy underpinning arms control is the reduction of tensions, risks as well as dangers without weakening deterrence. Arms control could also be guided by such thinking as the need to promote détente, to effect budget cuts, to preserve arms control momentum, to satisfy public opinion, to permit a shift of resources to non-defense programmes and so forth.

METHODS OF ARMS CONTROL

Arms control is easy to apply in the control of nuclear weapons. This is because the control of nuclear weapons is made possible in theory by the ability of major nuclear powers to reach the optimum of assured destruction beyond which it is irrational to go. In other words, major nuclear powers have attained the level of deterrence, which is the threat they pose to each other because of the availability of the number of nuclear warheads and invulnerable delivery systems necessary to destroy the military installations and industrial population centers of a prospective enemy.²⁷³

²⁷³ John Spanier, Games Nations Play, fifth edition, Rinehart-Winson, 1982. p 557

The first method of arms control for nations is to limit the production of nuclear weapons and delivery vehicles by unilateral action based upon their own judgment of what is enough in terms of deterrence or actual nuclear war. The United States employed this method by cutting back or discontinuing the production of certain types of missiles and airplanes during the cold war and the post-cold war era.

Secondly, nations can control their armaments by tacit agreement. This is done through one side's action or omission being predicated upon the other side's example, vice versa. For instance, during the 1960s, both the United States and The Soviet Union tacitly controlled their arms. The United States and the Soviet Union refrained from testing nuclear weapons in the atmosphere from 1958 to 1961.

Thirdly, nations can also control their armaments by formal agreement. This entails both parties coming together to conclude an agreement or treaty that would stipulate how arms will be controlled. For instance, the partial test ban treaty, concluded in 1963 by Great Britain, the Soviet Union and the United States is an example of a formal agreement aimed at arms control. The agreement prohibited the continuation of underground tests. 4

Fourthly, certain types or all kinds of weapons are excluded from certain geographical regions or groups of nations. Examples of this method include the Antarctic treaty of 1961, the Outer space treaty of 1967, the Latin American Nuclear Free Zone treaty of 1967, the Non-Proliferation treaty of 1970, the Sea-Bed treaty of 1971 and the convention on the prohibition of the development, production and stockpiling of bacteriological (biological) and toxic weapons of 1972.

Conventional weapons are a little less easy to control than nuclear weapons. According to Morgenthau, the quality and disposition of conventional weapons have a direct bearing upon the distribution of military power and since nations compete for military advantage, an agreement on the control of conventional weapons would signify the end of competition.

DISARMAMENT

Hans Morgenthau defines disarmament as the reduction or elimination of certain all armaments for the purpose of ending the armaments race.²⁸⁴ In making the distinction between disarmament and arms control, Morgenthau stresses that while disarmament is the reduction or elimination of armaments, arms control is concerned with regulating the armaments race for the purpose of creating a measure of military stability.

Dougherty and Pfaltzgraff say disarmament in the strict sense involves the destruction of armaments and prohibition against future production.²⁹⁵

In all, disarmament basically means to limit or eliminate the military or strategic strength of a nation, especially as such strength relates to its ability to wage war against another nation.

The first negotiation of this sort occurred in 1817, when the famous Rush-Bagot Agreement was reached, concerning arms on the Canadian-American boundary. The agreement was principally the work of President Monroe, and of Lord Castlereagh as foreign secretary. It pledged the United States and England to discontinue naval armaments on the Great Lakes. An arms race was threatening there; the memory of naval battles along the frontier was fresh from the two

²⁸⁴ Hans J. Morgenthau, Politics among nations. The struggle for power and peace, brief edition, New York; McGraw-Hill, Inc, 1993. p. 280.

²⁹⁵ Ibid. pp 280-281

recent wars, the American Revolution and the War of 1812. The agreement, which the United States senate approved by a unanimous vote, restricted both sides to one armed vessel on Lake Champlain, one on Lake Ontario, and to two on the upper lakes- Erie, Huron, Michigan, and Superior. The vessels were allowed to carry no more than one eighteen-pound gun apiece. The terms of the agreement are simpler, and more pleasing to report, than are some of the surrounding and following events. After 1817 land fortifications increased rather than decreased; later, when Anglo-American tensions occurred, ways were found to disrespect the spirit if not the letter of the naval agreement. Nevertheless the Rush-Bagot Agreement proved to be the acorn from which the present system of disarmed boundary keeping between Canada and the United States grew, in the course of half a century. By the time of the Anglo-American Treaty of Washington in 1871- the settlement which reduced the external tensions of the civil war decade- the policy of disarmament had been applied to the land frontier the same as to the water frontier.

A century later, the second time the United States had to be greatly concerned with reducing an arms race, the story became much more complex. World war I was three years over; the League of Nations had been founded, and the covenant pledged all members to a policy of disarmament. The United States had refused to join, yet Senator William Borah of Idaho, had been the man to press for the Naval Disarmament conference, which convened in Washington in 1921. The conference raised the hopes of the world. Under the chairmanship and leadership of Secretary of State Charles Evans Hughes, naval ratios were agreed upon for the capital ships of the United States, three European powers and Japan. The treaty proportions follow: the United States, 5; Great Britain, 5; Japan, 3; France, 1.75. Of course at that time the capacity of the world powers to aggress was still located in land and sea, and not in air force or missile

strength. So the ratios did truly establish for a decade, a limited form of arms control.

The Geneva conference of 1927, which was called by President Coolidge, accomplished nothing. A little later in 1930, the London Conference did achieve for the first time an agreement at limiting the building of cruisers and submarines; but the commitment was made only until 1936, and at that time it was allowed to expire. Another conference was held at Geneva, beginning early in 1932. President Hoover proposed, first, that all armaments capable of being used for offence be outlawed; when that proposal failed he suggested a 30 per cent arms reduction across the board. France rejected the Hoover ideas. But, before the meeting began, Japan had already launched the conquest of southern Manchuria; during its early months, Hitler seized power in Germany; and, between sessions in 1933, the Third Reich withdrew from the League of Nations. The disarmament effort following World War I withered and died under the heat of these events.

In sum, then, the short course of negotiated, bilateral or multilateral disarmament and arms control in the history of the United States- or indeed in the history of the west- concerns simply the one secure and lasting achievement, the Canadian-American one of the nineteenth century and since, and the efforts of the league and the five naval powers, between 1922 and 1936. Certainly the judgment, which historians habitually pass upon disarmament, is pessimistic.³⁰⁶

Largely, the failure of disarmament has been caused by a number of factors. Among these are; the hypocrisy of superpowers; mutual suspicion among states; belief in arms acquisition; struggle for regional supremacy by developing

³⁰⁶ Politics among nations. P. 279

countries; new countries seeing disarmament as an attempt to keep them under imperialism.

ISSUES IN ARMS CONTROL AND DISARMAMENT

A major issue as far as arms control and disarmament are concerned is the issue of asymmetry. On the asymmetry of military doctrine, it has been shown that it is very difficult to weigh the military doctrine of two states undergoing the process of arms control. This was a major problem that faced the process of arms control between the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) and the WARSAW pact because it was difficult to weigh the military doctrines of the two parties. For example, the military doctrine of NATO was defensive both in intention and capabilities. On the other hand, the philosophy of the WARSAW pact was defensive in intention but offensive in capability.

The problem of asymmetry of geography concerns mainly matters of location and size. Whenever nations consider the issue of arms control what readily comes to mind is the factor of strategic location. Those nations that are strategically located have more strength than those that are not. The size of a nation also gives it a kind of a geopolitical advantage in the distribution of powers. The Soviet Union (now RUSSIA) has derived much from this factor.

On the asymmetry of options available to nations, the point to note is that in a long process of arms procurements and training, some nations derive some advantages, which are not available to theirs. For instance, while it is clear that weapons can be eliminated, it is important to note that it is not easy to eliminate the knowledge, tactics and strategies already acquired by military experts.

Lastly, the asymmetry of forces is a major problem confronting arms control and disarmament. Nations of the world do not have equality in the distribution of their military forces. The problem was one of the issues that made it difficult for both the United States and the Soviet Union to properly control their arms during the cold war era.

Another major issue in arms control and disarmament is the failure associated with the various regulations related to arms control and disarmament. For instance, the disarmament negotiations of the 1920s, which had been focused on reducing arms to non-threatening levels failed disastrously. If this was the case with conventional weapons, the goals of arms control and disarmament had become very complex in the nuclear age. This is because, according to Kissinger, a safe level of nuclear weapons was almost a contradiction in the 1960s and 1970s when disarmament was subordinated to efforts aimed at reducing specific, definable dangers, of which the most prominent was the effort to prevent a surprise attack.

Another issue is that arms control tends to over simplify the problem of armament. To be sure, policy makers who plan for war or who take the decision to initiate nuclear war may not be scientists and therefore could not be familiar with some of the weapons.

Verification is another issue associated with arms control and disarmament. This is because it is not easy to determine the formulas of reduction, restructuring or redeployment of forces, which certainly require an intensity of verification.

All these difficulties have made Kissinger to conclude, “Arms control had become an abstruse subject involving esoteric five points that, even the best intentions, will take years to resolve”³¹⁷

THE SECURITY DILLEMA

It is a somber thought that at a time when so large a proportion of the human race remains near starvation level, about six percent of the world’s resources is still being devoted to military expenditure, with no serious likelihood of this situation fundamentally changing.

Social scientists will continue to seek basic causes in the hope of offering total solutions, but at the potential working level the explanation is simple enough. Any sovereign state- that is, any community which wishes to maintain a capacity for independent political action- may have to use or indicate its capacity and readiness to use forces-functional and purposive violence-to protect itself against coercion by other states. Given the state system, peace is possible only when there is freedom from all fear of coercion; and in the absence of any supranational authority enforcing a universal rule of law, such freedom from fear still depends at least partly on independent or collective military capability such is the conventional wisdom which will continue to rule mankind until we develop a viable alternative, or until there develops so strong a global sense of community that coercion, the use of force to impose one’s will on others becomes literally unthinkable. At present, unfortunately, such coercion is by no means unthinkable even within the most stable of communities and the most powerful of sovereign states.³²⁸

³¹⁷ Dougherty and Pfalzgraff. P. 413

³²⁸ Charles A Barker, Problems of World Disarmament. P. 3

It is generally believed that there are two ways to win an arms race. One is to outdo the opposition by sheer quantity of procurement. The other is to steal a march on them by developing some superlative new weapon. States have for long believed in the possession of arms as a means of security. Being asked to disarm puts them in a vulnerable position because there is no means of actually verifying the capabilities of all states. An eccentric leader could hide weapons of mass destruction anywhere in his state. As a result of land mass and lack of means to search an entire state, the mistrust is still there. As such states will find it difficult to completely disarm so as not to be put in a vulnerable position.

Those who believe that nuclear abolition is possible are criticized for their utopian view of the world. Brent Scowcroft and Arnold Kanter in a 1997 Washington Times article ask how nuclear knowledge can be magically forgotten. Many believe that the Cold War was kept cold because of mutually assured destruction, the idea that a country can strike back and pose an equal or larger amount of damage for the aggressor.³³⁹

³³⁹ Omon M. Osiki in Femi Adegulu, Topics and issues in International Relations.pp 87-88

CHAPTER FIVE

NUCLEAR DETERRENCE AND THE FUTURE

Nuclear deterrence is a strategy aimed at preventing attack by having effective second-strike capability. According to T. C. Shelling (1963), it is a particular type of social and political relationship in which one party tries to influence the behavior of another in a desired direction.

The period from 1945 to 1990 saw the gradual development of nuclear deterrence as the mainstay of international peace and security, even though arousing much disquiet about its moral basis and acute anxiety over its dangers.

In the post-war era, deterrence has attained a pre-eminence. The existence of nuclear weaponry was responsible for this pre-eminence. Defeating an enemy on the battlefield was no longer a prerequisite for inflicting enormous casualties on his civilian population, disrupting the administrative apparatus of his state or destroying his industrial wealth. As such, war prevention had, by and large, superseded victory during hostilities as the main objective of nuclear powers.

Deterrence was developed as a means of protecting vital security interests and upholding international order while at the same time preventing war. It was almost at times regarded as a panacea, as the answer to most of the West's security problems in the struggle against the communist states.

The intellectual context within which the notion of deterrence was nurtured and developed was dominated by the problems of the cold war and the bipolar relationship between the superpowers. Throughout the 1950's the main problems centered on Washington's ability to prevent Soviet aggression against

either the United State's homeland itself or that of America's allies in Europe and Asia.

Deterrence can be seen as a particular type of social or political relationship in which one party tries to influence the behavior of another in desired directions. It, however, involves a particularly distinctive type of influence that rests directly and openly upon threats of sanctions and deprivations. Basically, it is an attempt by party A to prevent party B from undertaking a course of action which A regards as undesirable, by threatening to inflict unacceptable costs upon B in the event that that action is taken. This crude definition captures the essence of the concept. The definition shows that deterrence is an attempt by party A to influence the intentions, and consequently the actual behavior, of party B in a particular direction- that of inaction. The attempt at exerting influence is very much a psychological phenomenon. It does not involve physically obstructing a certain course of action, but making that action appear costly and unattractive.³⁴¹

The nuclear age has come with its own peculiar problems. Since the end of the Cold War, it has been argued that there are more nuclear actors on the world stage to worry about. Particularly, a number of states defined as "rogue" states have entered the scene, with a propensity for violence and the disruption of peace (Henriksen 1999). Iraq, Iran, North Korea, Cuba, and Libya are some of these "rogue" states. They are threats to their neighbors, the world, and the United States. (Policy.com 1999/2000)

PROBLEMS OF DETERRENCE

Scholars have argued as to whether deterrence as a principle of arms control really works. For instance, Stanley Siekiewicz believes that a nuclear aggressor

³⁴¹ Causes of War. P. 16

planning an attack does not know whether the potential victim will launch vulnerable retaliatory forces as soon as it is clear that an attack is underway, nor can the aggressors predict how the enemy's command and control system will function, and how well the retaliatory forces will operate. [Stanley Sienkiewicz, cited in Dougherty and Pfaltzgraff, p 397]

Holsti has warned that “no system of deterrence is likely to prove effective against a nation led by a trigger-happy paranoid, or by someone seeking personal or national self-destruction or martyrdom, or by decision makers willing to play a form of international Russian roulette, or by leaders whose information about and communication with an adversary are so incomplete that their decision making processes are dominated by guesswork, or by those who regard the loss of most of their nation's population and resources as a reasonable cost for the achievement of foreign policy goals.[holsti, cited in Dougherty and Pfaltzgraff, p397]

CONCLUSION

Kenneth N. Waltz asserts that the spread of nuclear weapons will induce greater stability since new nuclear states will use their weapons to deter other states from attacking them.

Scott D. Sagan argues that instability will result from the further spread of nuclear weapons because of greater potential for preventive nuclear wars and serious nuclear weapon accidents.

The invention of gruesome weapons and the threat they bring have not caused people to recoil with horror and disband their troops. On the contrary, weapons have heightened fear among states and non-state actors to further weapon accumulation. It is based on this that arms control and disarmament are a sine qua non for effective management and control of arms and other uses.

It is evident that possession of arms does not necessarily lead to war, as deterrence does not lead to peace. Also that disarmament cannot be completely carried out in its totality due to fear and insecurity.

A major difficulty in arriving at agreement even between states that desire disarmament is that they naturally desire disarmament with security. In other words, they reject the simple notion that disarmament will guarantee security and demand, on the contrary, a framework of security as a precondition for disarmament. If disarmament is to be total, the problem is one of creating a system of world government. For there must be some kind of force to impose order and control of that force would confer world domination.

On nuclear weapons, the application of deterrence has helped to avert the outbreak of nuclear war by eliminating the incentive to strike first at the other

side. In all, arms control, which implies any measure limiting or reducing forces, regulating armaments and restricting the deployment of troops or weapons, can and has been relevant to world peace and security. Similarly, disarmament, which is the agreement to reduce or abolish existing military forces or weapons, can also contribute to world peace and security.

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